

Syntheses of 1,5-benzothiazepines : Part-XXXIV. Syntheses and antimicrobial studies of 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(4-methoxyphenyl/3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines

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Manuscript received 27 December 2006, revised 19 September 2007, accepted 17 December 2007

Abstract : Reactions of the 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols 4a-f with the α,β -unsaturated heterocyclic ketones 3a,b were carried out in dry ethanol saturated with dry HCl gas. The products 5a-l were characterized by microestimations for C, H, N, S and IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, ¹⁹F NMR and mass spectral studies. The synthesized compounds were screened for antimicrobial activity against the bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and the fungus, *Candida albicans*. All the compounds showed moderate activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with reference to standard drugs, gatifloxin and natilmicin but showed good activity against the fungus, *Candida albicans* with reference drug fluconazole. The maximum antifungal activity has been shown by the compound 5k having maximum number of methoxyl groups and 5g and 5a having fluoro in addition to methoxyl groups.

Keywords : Cardiovascular, 1,5-benzothiazepines, diltiazem, methoxyphenyl.

Introduction

The well-established cardiovascular drug known worldwide¹⁻³, 'diltiazem' and its further improved versions^{4,5} 'clentiazem' and 'siratiazem' have methoxyphenyl group in 1,5-benzothiazepine nucleus. The anti-tumour drug⁶, 'zimet' has two methoxyl groups in the benzopyranobenzodiazepine nucleus. The presence of methoxyphenyl group in bicyclic 1,5-benzothiazepine drugs and the presence of two methoxyl groups in tetracyclic benzopyranobenzodiazepine drug⁶, interested us to synthesize bicyclic 1,5-benzothiazepines⁷⁻¹³ and analogous tetracyclic benzopyranobenzothiazepines^{14,15} having increased number of methoxyl groups, two, three and four. The compound having maximum number of methoxyl groups has been found to show high antifungal activity¹⁵.

1,5-Benzothiazepines having heterocyclic groups as substituents have been reported to exhibit antibacterial, antifungal and insecticidal activities^{16,17}. In our other studies, 1,5-benzothiazepine compounds, having thienyl group, showed¹⁸ moderate to good antibacterial alongwith antifungal activity.

It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to synthesize

bicyclic 1,5-benzothiazepines having one, two and three methoxyl groups alongwith a thienyl group and evaluate their antimicrobial activity. A series of 1,5-benzothiazepines having methoxyphenyl or dimethoxyphenyl group at position 2, heterocyclic group as thienyl, at position 4 and halogen, alkyl or alkoxy at position 8, have been synthesized and studies comprising antibacterial and antifungal are reported in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The chalcone analogues, 3-(4-methoxyphenyl/3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3a,b**) were obtained by the reaction of 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (**1a**) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (**1b**) with acetylthiophene (**2**). Equimolar quantities of six 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols (**4a-f**) and α,β -unsaturated heterocyclic ketones (**3a,b**) were refluxed in dry ethanol saturated with dry HCl gas for 6-10 h to obtain the title compounds **5a-l** in 60-70% yields in a single step (Table 1). These type of reactions are reported to take place by nucleophilic attack by sulphhydryl electrons of the 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols on the β -carbon atom of

Table 1. Physical constants and analytical data of compounds **5b-i**, **5k** and **5l**

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula (Mol. wt.)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	S
5b	145-146	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ OS ₂ NCl (385.5)	-	-	3.57 (3.63)	-
5c	140-141	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ OS ₂ NBr (430)	-	-	3.22 (3.25)	14.78 (14.88)
5d	158-159	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ OS ₂ N (365)	-	-	3.79 (3.83)	17.49 (17.53)
5e	135-136	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₂ S ₂ N (381)	6.09 (6.14)	4.89 (4.98)	3.61 (3.67)	-
5f	60-61	45	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ S ₂ N (395)	66.87 (66.83)	5.27 (5.31)	-	-
5g	88-89	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ S ₂ NF (399)	63.02 (63.15)	4.42 (4.51)	-	15.62 (16.04)
5h	142-143	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ S ₂ NCl (415.5)	-	-	3.22 (3.37)	-
5i	140-141	67	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ S ₂ NBr (460)	-	-	3.00 (3.04)	-
5k	170-171	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ S ₂ N (411)	-	-	3.47 (3.40)	15.52 (15.57)
5l	118-119	67	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ S ₂ N (425)	65.62 (64.94)	5.42 (5.41)	3.68 (3.29)	14.86 (15.06)

the α,β -unsaturated ketones to give Michael adducts which undergo cyclization to afford the final compounds^{7-15,18-21} (Scheme 1).

The IR spectra of final products **5a-l**, did not show absorption bands in the region at 3445-3200 and 1690-1650 cm⁻¹, characteristic of NH₂ and C=O group respectively but gave absorption bands at 3150-3140 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to secondary amino group. The intermediates (shown in parenthesis) formed by the reaction of **4a-f** with **3a** and **3b** could not be isolated indicating thereby that the reactions take place in a single step as observed earlier²².

In the ¹H NMR spectra, singlet absorption peak at around δ 3.88 were assigned to one methoxyl protons of compounds **5a-f** and two singlet peaks of three protons each in compounds **5g-l** at δ 3.92-3.98 correspond to the presence of two methoxyl group protons. A doublet of C-2-H at δ 6.88-6.96 (*J* 8 Hz) and another doublet of C-3-H at δ 7.98-8.14 (*J* 8 Hz) indicated the formation of 2,5-dihydro derivatives^{7-13,18}. The aromatic protons absorbed as multiplets in the region δ 6.79-8.02 (Table 2).

In ¹³C NMR studies, besides absorptions observed at around δ_c 77.0 due to CDCl₃ carbon, **5g** exhibited two methoxyl carbons at δ 55.98 and 56.52. Absorption of

other carbons were observed at δ 109.6, 110.2, 111.1, 111.8, 119.5, 120.9, 121.7, 122.5, 123.7, 127.7, 127.8, 128.5, 131.2, 131.9, 132.1, 133.5, 145.8, 149.2 and 151.5. In the ¹⁹F NMR spectra, single absorption peak at δ -114.2 and δ -113.00 observed for compounds **5a** and **5g** respectively were due to fluorine.

In the mass spectrum of **5b**, *m/z*, [M]⁺ at 385 and [M+2]⁺ of almost one third intensity at 387 and that of **5h** [M]⁺ at 415 and [M+2]⁺ at 417, correspond to their respective molecular masses, the [M+2]⁺ peak signifying isotopic chlorine. The compound **5c** showed *m/z*, [M]⁺ at 429 and [M+2]⁺ of almost equal intensity at 431 and likewise, **5i** gave [M]⁺ at 459 and [M+2]⁺ at 461 which correspond to their respective masses. The results of elemental analysis were found to be satisfactory, being within the permissible limits of error (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity : All the synthesized compounds (**5a-l**) were screened for antifungal activity against the fungus *Candida albicans* and antibacterial activity against the gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and the gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, at the concentration of 100 μ g/disc, using the paper disc method²³, with fluconazole, gatifloxin and natilmicin, as the reference compounds respectively. The reference com-

Compd.	X	R
5a	F	4-OCH ₃
5b	Cl	4-OCH ₃
5c	Br	4-OCH ₃
5d	CH ₃	4-OCH ₃
5e	OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃
5f	OC ₂ H ₅	4-OCH ₃

Compd.	X	R
5g	F	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂
5h	Cl	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂
5i	Br	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂
5j	CH ₃	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂
5k	OCH ₃	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂
5l	OC ₂ H ₅	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂

Scheme 1

pounds were used to evaluate the relative activity in the form of activity index. Zone of inhibition, exhibited by the reference and test compounds were measured and relative activities were calculated as activity index.

Activity index =

$$\frac{\text{Zone of inhibition exhibited by test compound}}{\text{Zone of inhibition exhibited by the reference compound}}$$

Antibacterial activity : Nutrient agar is used as culture media, prepared by taking a mixture of agar-agar (15 g/L), NaCl (5 g/L), beef extract (1.5 g/L), yeast extract (1.5 g/L) and peptic digest of animal tissues (5 g/L) dissolved in distilled water. The pH of culture media was maintained at 7.4 ± 0.2 . The media was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 pounds/cm² for 15 min and poured in petri plates. The petri plates were inoculated with bac-

Table 2. Characteristic ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ values in ppm) signals of compounds **5b-i**, **5k** and **5l**

Compd.	OCH ₃ (3H, s)	N-H (1H, br)	C-2-H (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz)	C-3-H (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz)	C-8-XH	Aryl H (m)
5b	3.82	4.25	6.97	7.99	–	7.00–7.96
5c	3.89	4.15	6.88	8.00	–	6.96–7.98
5d	3.88	4.16	6.98	8.024	2.48 (3H, s)	7.00–8.00
5e	3.87	4.12	6.96	8.01	3.89 (3H, s)	7.05–7.99
5f	3.82	4.06	6.92	7.98	1.40 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6 Hz) 4.07 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6 Hz)	6.98–7.92
5g	3.94 3.90	4.30	6.87	7.98	–	6.85–7.88
5h	3.95 3.93	4.00	6.89	7.87	–	6.83–7.91
5i	3.98 3.94	4.38	6.67	7.98	–	6.85–7.67
5k	3.94 3.93	4.12	6.77	7.77	3.83 (3H, s)	6.82–7.85
5l	3.95 3.92	4.20	6.94	8.14	1.42 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6 Hz) 4.07 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6 Hz)	6.91–7.90

terial suspension and incubated for 30 min. Filter paper discs of test compounds were placed on these plates and incubated for 40 h at 37 °C. Zone of inhibition measured and compared with standard compounds to show the results as activity index given in parenthesis (Table 3).

Antifungal activity : The sabouraud dextrose agar media is used as culture media, prepared by a mixture of mycological peptone (10 g/L), dextrose (40 g/L) and agar-agar (15 g/L) in distilled water. The pH of the culture media was maintained at 5.6 ± 0.2. It was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 pounds/cm² pressure for 15 min and poured in petri plates. The petri plates were inoculated by even streaking of fungal suspension. The filter paper discs were placed onto these plates and incubated for 40 h at 37 °C. Zone of inhibitions were recorded and compared with zone of inhibition exhibited by reference compound to determine activity index given in parenthesis (Table 3).

All the synthesized compounds **5a-l**, were found to show moderate activity against the bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* but good activity against the fungus *Candida albicans*. Maximum antifungal activity was shown by compound **5k** having maximum number of methoxy substituents. It did not show activity against gram-negative bacteria, *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa and has insignificant activity against gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus*. It indicates that methoxy substituents may impart an important role against the fungus but not against bacteria, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by TLC on glass plates coated with silica gel 'G' using benzene : ethanol : aq. ammonia (50%) (7 : 2 : 1) as solvent system. The IR spectra were taken in KBr pellets on a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard.

The FAB mass spectra were recorded on JEOL-SX 102/DA-6000, Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix. Microestimations for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were carried out in Elemental Analyzer, Carlo Erba 1108. The spectral analysis and elemental analysis were carried out at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility (SAIF), Central Drug

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of compounds **5a-l**
(Zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
5a	12 (0.54)	12 (0.5)	18 (1.28)
5b	-	19 (0.79)	16 (1.14)
5c	20 (0.91)	20 (0.83)	15 (1.07)
5d	22 (1.00)	15 (0.62)	14 (1.00)
5e	10 (0.45)	8 (0.33)	16 (1.14)
5f	10 (0.45)	14 (0.58)	8 (0.57)
5g	12 (0.54)	12 (0.5)	18 (1.28)
5h	16 (0.73)	18 (0.75)	16 (1.14)
5i	-	18 (0.75)	14 (1.00)
5j	24 (1.09)	12 (0.5)	14 (1.00)
5k	8 (0.36)	-	18 (1.28)
5l	10 (0.45)	12 (0.5)	-

Values in parentheses represent activity index.

Zone of inhibition exhibited by Gatifloxin for *Staphylococcus aureus* is 22 mm.

Zone of inhibition exhibited by Natilmicin for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 24 mm.

Zone of inhibition exhibited by Fluconazole for *Candida albicans* is 14 mm.

Research Institute, Lucknow. Antimicrobial studies were carried out at Microbiology Department, S. M. S. Medical College, Jaipur.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (3a) : Equimolar quantities of 2-acetylthiophene (**2**) and 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (**1a**) were mixed in dry ethanol and stirred at room temperature. On dropwise addition of 10% NaOH with continued stirring, the colour of the reaction mixture changed into yellow and finally gave solid. The crude solid thus obtained was crystallized from dry methanol to give 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3a**) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 79–80 °C, yield 78%, R_f 0.78; IR (KBr) ν (cm⁻¹) : 1645 (C=O),

1620 (C=C), 3000 (aromatic C-H), 2930 (aliphatic C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 3.93 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.7^a–7.87 (7H, m, aromatic H) (Found : C, 68.80; H, 5.88; S, 13.08. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂O₂S (244) : C, 68.85; H, 4.91; S, 13.11%).

3-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (3b) : 2-Acetylthiophene (**2**) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (**1b**) were mixed in dry ethanol in equimolar quantities. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature and 10% NaOH was added in a dropwise manner till the colour changed to yellow. The reaction mixture was kept in refrigerator for 24 h. The crude product thus obtained was purified by crystallization from methanol to afford yellow crystals of 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3b**), m.p. 88–89 °C, yield 80%, R_f 0.87; IR (KBr) ν (cm⁻¹) : 1646 (C=O), 1625 (C=C), 3025 (aromatic C-H), 2940 (aliphatic C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 3.93 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.78–7.87 (6H, m, aromatic H) (Found : C, 65.60; H, 5.11; S, 11.69. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄O₃S (274) : C, 65.69; H, 5.10; S, 11.67%).

2,5-Dihydro-8-fluoro-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (5a) : Equimolar quantities of 2-amino-5-fluorobenzenethiol (**4a**) and 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3a**) were refluxed in dry ethanol saturated with dry HCl gas for 8 h. The crude solid obtained on removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, on crystallization from dry methanol, gave 2,5-dihydro-8-fluoro-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (**5a**), m.p. 98–99 °C; yield 64%, R_f 0.78; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.00 (1H, br, NH), 6.96 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, C-2-H), 8.01 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, C-3-H), 7.05–7.99 (10H, m, aromatic H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 56.52, 76.98, 77.4, 110.2, 111.2, 118.8, 119.5, 120.9, 121.3, 122.2, 123.1, 127.7, 127.8, 128.1, 131.5, 131.8, 132.1, 133.5, 145.7, 149.2, 151.5; ¹⁹F NMR (CDCl₃) δ : -114.42 (Found : C, 64.98; H, 4.25; N, 3.71; S, 17.29. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆OS₂NF (369) : C, 65.04; H, 4.33; N, 3.79; S, 17.34%).

8-Fluoro-2,5-dihydro-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (5g) : 2-Amino-5-fluorobenzenethiol (**4a**) and 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3b**) were taken in equimolar quantities in dry ethanol saturated with dry HCl gas and refluxed for 8 h. On completion of the reaction the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain crude solid which was crystallized by dry ethanol to obtain 8-fluoro-2,5-dihydro-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-

1,5-benzothiazepine (**5g**), m.p. 88–89 °C; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 56.52, 55.98, 76.98, 77.4, 109.6, 110.2, 111.1, 111.8, 119.5, 120.9, 121.7, 122.5, 123.7, 127.7, 127.8, 128.5, 131.2, 131.9, 132.1, 133.5, 145.8, 149.2, 151.5; ^{19}F NMR (CDCl_3) δ : -113.0.

2,5-Dihydro-8-methyl-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (**5j**) : 2-Amino-5-methylbenzenethiol (**4d**, 0.001 mol) and 3-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(2-thienyl)-2-propenone (**3b**, 0.001 mol) were dissolved in dry ethanol and saturated with dry HCl gas, refluxed for 9 h and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain crude solid which was crystallized from dry ethanol to obtain, 2,5-dihydro-8-methyl-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (**5j**), m.p. 61–62 °C, yield 62%, R_f 0.76; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 3.94 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.97 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.00 (1H, br, NH), 6.91 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, C-2-H), 8.06 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, C-3-H), 7.01–7.94 (9H, m, aromatic H) (Found : C, 66.78; H, 5.27; N, 3.48; S, 16.24. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}$ (395) : C, 66.83; H, 5.31; N, 3.54; S, 16.20%).

By following similar procedures the compounds **5b-f**, **5h-i**, **5k** and **5l** were prepared. Their physical, microanalytical and spectral datas are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial assistance provided by the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, UGC Central Regional Office, Bhopal and CSIR, New Delhi. Thanks are also due to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan and the Principal, L. B. S. Government P. G. College, Kotputli, Jaipur, for providing the facility to work and the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for providing the elemental analysis and spectral data.

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